

Oxidation of Cyclanols by Cr^{vi} in Ternary Solvent Mixtures*

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The kinetics of oxidation of cyclanols by Cr^{vi} in ternary solvent mixtures is reported. The reaction rate is dependent largely on dielectric constant. Structural factors indicate that the reactivity is of the order :

The relative order in bicyclic alcohols is Iso-Borneol > Borneol. The rates are quite consistent with either the ester or the hydride ion abstraction hypothesis postulated by previous workers.

The role of ternary solvent mixtures in oxidations with Cr^{vi} has not been studied. In the present investigation, the kinetics of oxidation of cyclic alcohols is reported in acetic acid—nitrobenzene—water, acetic acid—pyridine—water and acetic acid—carbon tetrachloride—water, under conditions of constant ionic strength and pH.

EXPERIMENTAL

The cyclanols were all Fluka products (AR). The procedure for kinetic study consisted in estimating the unreacted Cr^{vi} by iodometry. The oxidation was carried out in binary and ternary solvent mixtures. Nitrobenzene, carbon-tetrachloride and pyridine were of AR grade. Ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 M by acetate buffer and pH 3.5 for all the oxidations. All the solvents were independently checked for any oxidation but there was none. The products are ketones and the stoichiometry for the oxidation of the alcohols to ketones is 2 : 3 M.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TABLE I

Second order rate constants ($k \times 10^3 \text{ l moles}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) for the oxidation of Cyclanols

Temperature 50°

Solvent	Composition	D	Iso-propanol	Cyclohexanol	Cyclopentanol	Cycloheptanol	Cyclooctanol
50% v/v 50% v/v	acetic acid + water	43.34	3.817	6.677	11.28	—	—
50% v/v 40% v/v 10% v/v	acetic acid + nitrobenzene + water	24.86	10.61	20.83	34.61	66.02	93.99
50% v/v 40% v/v 10% v/v	acetic acid + pyridine + water	15.85	31.36	58.91	121.7	159.3	352.7
90% v/v 10% v/v	acetic acid + water	13.49	45.25	81.58	130.2	218.6	—

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The second order rate constants show that the sequence of oxidation is

The greater reactivity of the five, seven and eight membered cyclic alcohols than that of cyclohexanol is in general accord with earlier investigations of Brown and co-workers¹ on the solvolysis of tosylates and SN_2 displacement of alicyclic halides. A qualitative interpretation has been suggested by them on the basis of I-strain in these rings, according to which reaction rates are determined by the difference in ring strain between the ground state and the transition state of the molecule in the process concerned. In cyclic systems changes in bond hybridization may produce concomitant changes in angle strain (Baeyer strain), bond opposition strain (torsional or Pitzer strain) or transannular strain. On the other hand, it has been proposed by Prelog and Heck⁹ that the rate maximum in the medium rings in these processes could at least in part be due to the effects of bonding character. According to this view the rate maximum in medium ring compounds could be due to the stabilization of an intermediate non-classical ion by synartetic participation of a transannular hydrogen atom.

A similar variation in kinetic rate constant with ring size was noticed by Rocek and Mares² in the chromic acid oxidation of cycloparaffins. The authors have suggested that the reactivity of alicyclic compounds is directly related to thermochemical strains of

Fig. I—*a* = Cyclohexanol; *b* = Cyclopentanol; *c* = Cycloheptanol; *d* = Cyclooctanol.

molecules and it is unnecessary to invoke any assumptions regarding the energy differences between the ground and the transition states. A plot of $\log k$ (oxidation) against the strain energy of cycloparaffins (*loc. cit.*) (Fig. I) shows linearity.

1. H. C. Brown, R. S. Fletcher and R. B. Johanssen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 212.
2. J. Rocek, F. Mares and J. Sicher, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1961, **26**, 2355.

Reaction mechanism : A plot of $\log k$ (oxidation) against $\log k$ (solvolysis of tosylates) (Fig. II) shows fair linearity. This shows that there is some similarity between the oxidation process and the solvolytic reaction indicating some carbonium ion character in the transition state. From a comparison of the oxidation reaction and its reverse reaction, namely, the borohydride reduction of the cyclic ketones it is shown that the former is favoured where the transition state has got a dominant carbonium ion character. A plot of

Fig. II—*a* = Cyclohexanol; *b* = Cyclopentanol; *c* = Cycloheptanol; *d* = Cyclooctanol.

$\log k$ (oxidation) against $\log k$ (borohydride reduction) (Fig. III) shows linearity. It is to be noted that the extent of variation of kinetic rate constant in these cyclanol oxidations is not so pronounced as in solvolysis reactions indicating probably that these are not pure SN_1 type reactions. A parallel study of oxidation of borneol and iso-borneol was also carried out

Fig. III—*a* = Cyclohexanol; *b* = Cyclopentanol; *c* = Cycloheptanol; *d* = Cyclooctanol.

in order to decide whether the reaction goes through a free carbonium ion or whether it is a process having a large SN_1 character. If it is the former, there should be a large

difference in the rate constants of oxidation of borneol and iso-borneol and if it is the latter the difference would be small. The calculated rate constants are given below.

TABLE II

Second order rate constants ($k \times 10^3$) l mole⁻¹ min⁻¹ for the oxidation of bicyclic secondary alcohols

Solvent	Composition	D	Borneol	Iso-Borneol	Ratio	Temperature 50°
50% v/v acetic acid + 50% v/v water		43.34	7.288	11.37	~1.5	
50% v/v acetic acid + 40% v/v nitrobenzene + 10% v/v water		24.86	20.34	26.18	~1.4	
70% v/v acetic acid + 20% v/v nitrobenzene + 10% v/v water		19.13	—	49.46		
50% v/v acetic acid + 40% v/v pyridine + 10% v/v water		15.85	52.14	72.02	~1.4	
70% v/v acetic acid + 20% v/v carbon tetrachloride + 10% v/v water		12.61	—	92.49		
90% v/v acetic acid + 10 v/v water		13.49	71.72	105.6	~1.4	

It is indeed clear from the Table II that the rates are normal and there is no neighbouring group participation as observed in solvolytic reactions of these systems. Iso-borneol is more reactive since the hydroxyl group suffers the non-bonded repulsion from the gem-dimethyl group and the faster rate can be explained as due to enhanced relief of the steric strain in the transition state. The data can be explained by either the ester or the hydride ion abstraction mechanism postulated by previous workers^{3,4,8}.

Solvent effects : A reference to Tables I and II shows that as the dielectric constant is decreased the reaction rates are faster both in binary solvent and ternary solvent mixtures. The dependence of the rate on the solvent composition may be explained by the approaches of both Ingold as well as Laidler and Amis. The present investigations are unfortunately handicapped by the non-availability of any value of dielectric constant of binary and ternary mixtures. Attempts to determine these values have not been fruitful probably because of the high conductivity of these systems and consequent low Q for a tuned circuit having such a low resistance across the condenser. Therefore the dielectric constants of these

3. S. V. Anantakrishnan and N. Venkatasubramanian, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1960, **51**, 310.
4. J. Rocek and J. Krupicka, *Coll. Czech. Commun.*, 1958, **23**, 2068.
5. K. B. Wiberg and R. J. Evans, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3019.
6. E. S. Amis, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, **27**, 1672.
7. R. A. Robinson and R. H. Stokes, "Electrolytic solutions", Butterworth Publications, London, 1955.
8. F. H. Westheimer and W. Watanabe, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1949, **17**, 61.

mixtures have been computed assuming a linear relationship in the range of solvent compositions used in the present work. Such an approximation has been made by Wiberg and Evans⁵.

A plot of $\log k$ against the reciprocal of dielectric constant (Fig. IV) gives a linear relationship for iso-borneol. According to Amis equation⁶:

$$\log k_{D=D} = \log k'_{D=\infty} + \frac{Ze\mu}{2.303 Dk T r^2}$$

The slope of the line obtained by plotting $\log k$ against $1/D$ would correspond to $\frac{Ze\mu}{2.303 k T r^2}$ and should give reasonable values of the parameter. The validity of this equation has been well established in the case of alkaline and acid hydrolysis of a number of esters.

Fig. IV.—*a* = 50% v/v acetic acid + 50% v/v water.

b = 50% v/v acetic acid + 40% v/v nitrobenzene + 10% v/v water.

c = 70% v/v acetic acid + 20% v/v nitrobenzene + 10% v/v water.

d = 50% v/v acetic acid + 40% v/v pyridine + 10% v/v water.

e = 70% v/v acetic acid + 20% v/v carbon tetrachloride + 10% v/v water.

f = 90% v/v acetic acid + 10% v/v water.

The value of “*r*” (molecular radius) obtained in the present studies are of the right order of magnitude and thus confirms the correctness of the approach. This establishes that it is an iondipolar reaction.

TABLE III

Compound	Slope	μ	Molecular radius <i>r</i> (Angstroms)
Iso-propanol	20.95	1.78	2.0
Cyclopentanol	22.07	1.34	1.7
Cyclohexanol	21.48	2.07	2.12

A complete explanation of the role of solvent in chemical reactions cannot be offered on the basis of dielectric constants of the media alone, although certain macroscopic properties of the solvent like the dielectric constant are of importance in determining the effect of solvent changes on reaction rate. Such macroscopic properties are often inadequate for a complete explanation of solvent effects. Robinson and Stokes⁷ state that the bulk dielectric constant is entirely different from the internal dielectric constant especially in low dielectric media. The selective solvation and the greater electrostatic attraction of the solute for the more polar component of the mixed solvents may produce near the solute particle a region of dielectric constant which is different from the bulk dielectric constant. Solute solvent interaction may be yet another factor in addition to dielectric constant. In these oxidations the solvation of the transition complex is smaller than the solvation of the reactants due to dispersal of charges in the transition state. A decrease in the rate of oxidation on the addition of more polar solvent in the present investigation is a natural result of the progressive increase in solvation of the reactant, more than that of the transition complex resulting in a lower rate of the reaction. Alternatively the considerable retardation in rate in solvent mixtures containing the more polar component could be traced to a short carbonium ion life in such relatively more nucleophilic media.

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